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NON-LINEAR TRANSIENT ANALYSIS OF LAMINATED PLATES SUBJECTED TO TRANSVERSE LOW-VELOCITY IMPACT

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ABSTRACT: Incorporating a modified Hertz contact law, a B-spline finite strip model is developed in the context of a layer-wise plate theory for analysing the geometrically non-linear response of laminated composite plates to transverse low-velocity impact. The model includes the geometrical non-linearity through use of von Karman's non-linear strain-displacement relationship. The resulting non-linear dynamic problem is solved using the Newmark time-stepping scheme together with Newton-Raphson iteration. Several numerical applications are described and a close comparison is found between the results calculated through the present model and the existing analytical and experimental results.

KEYWORDS: Laminated Composite, Low-velocity Impact, Geometrical non-linearity, Transient, Finite Strip

1. INTRODUCTION

Laminated composite structures have played an important role in aircraft, vehicles and many other demanding applications because of their high strength-to-weight and high stiffness-to-weight ratios. As it is well known, however, these structures are very susceptible to low-velocity impact damage, which can be introduced during manufacture and in service. Impact induced damage can have a significant effect on the strength, stability and reliability of the structures. Therefore, great concern has been gained on the low-velocity impact of the structures [1]. For understanding the initiation and propagation of the damage it is very important to have an insight into dynamic response of the impacted structures. Numerous analysis techniques have been used to study the impact response of the structures varying from finite element method [2-5] to analytical approaches based on series expansion [6-9]. It appears that the majority of previous analytical and numerical analyses are limited to small-deflection behaviour. Although such linear analyses are practical and useful for many impact problems of composite structures, it is often the case that the geometric non-linearity has very significant effects on the impact response.

In the present paper, the earlier layer-wise B-spline finite strip model [10,11] is extended through introduction of time dimension for the impact problem of laminated composite plate subjected to transverse low-velocity impact of spherical object. The geometrical non-linearity is counted into consideration by use of von Karman's non-linear strain-displacement relationship. The dynamic problem is solved using the Newmark time-stepping scheme in the time domain and the solution of the resulting non-linear equations is sought with Newton-Raphson iteration. The impact problem in condition of small-deflection is briefly discussed as well. Several numerical applications are presented.

2. FORMULATION

2.1. BASIC IMPACT PROBLEM AND PLATE EQUATIONS

Consider a laminated rectangular plate with arbitrary lay-ups subjected to transverse low-velocity impact of a spherical object as shown in Fig. 1. The impactor is of radius r_s , mass m

and velocity v_0 . It is assumed that the vibrations of the elastic impactor can be neglected. An orthogonal Cartesian co-ordinate system x_i ($i=1,2,3$) is used in this paper.

Fig. 1. Transverse impact on a rectangular plate

In the present study, the layer-wise plate theory proposed by Reddy [12] is adopted for representation of displacement behaviour in the plate. Through the thickness direction, the laminated plate is divided into a desired number, N , of numerical layers, which can be less than, equal to, or greater than the number of physical layers. The assumed displacements (\bar{u}_a , \bar{u}_3) at a general point of the laminate, with t as the time dimension, take the form as what follows.

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{u}_\alpha(x_\beta, x_3, t) &= u_\alpha(x_\beta, t) + \Psi^i(x_3)u_\alpha^i(x_\beta, t) \\ \bar{u}_3(x_\beta, x_3, t) &= u_3(x_\beta, t)\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

Where the usual Cartesian indicial notation is adopted. The Greek subscripts, which take values 1 and 2, and subscript 3 refer to x_1 , x_2 , x_3 directions, respectively. Repeated indices imply the summation convention. Superscript i , ranged from 1 to N , is related to the nodes through the thickness. u_a and u_3 denote the three displacement components of the reference plane ($x_3=0$). Ψ^i are piecewise continuous functions defined in terms of linear Lagrange interpolation functions.

The expressions of the strain-displacement relationship can be given by substitution of the displacement field (1) in the Green's expressions for in-plane non-linear strains and neglecting higher order terms in a manner consistent with von Karmon's assumptions. They are

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{\epsilon}_{\alpha\beta} &= \epsilon_{\alpha\beta} + \mathcal{O}^i \epsilon_{\alpha\beta}^i \\ \bar{\gamma}_{\alpha 3} &= \gamma_{\alpha 3} + \mathcal{O}^i \gamma_{\alpha 3}^i\end{aligned}\quad (2)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_{\alpha\beta} &= \frac{1}{2}(u_{\alpha,\beta} + u_{\beta,\alpha}) + \frac{1}{2}u_{3,\alpha}u_{3,\beta} \\ \epsilon_{\alpha\beta}^i &= \frac{1}{2}(u_{\alpha,\beta}^i + u_{\alpha,\beta}^i) \\ \gamma_{\alpha 3} &= u_{3,\alpha} \quad \gamma_{\alpha 3}^i = u_\alpha^i\end{aligned}\quad (3)$$

The strain energy of the laminate considered can be obtained as an integral over the reference plane area S . The result is

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \iint_S (N_{ab} e_{ab} + N_{ab}^i e_{ab}^i + Q_{a3} g_{a3} + Q_{a3}^j g_{a3}^j) dx_1 dx_2 \quad (4)$$

$$\text{where } \begin{Bmatrix} N_{ab} \\ N_{ab}^i \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{abgw} & B_{abgw}^k \\ B_{abgw}^i & D_{abgw}^{ik} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} e_{gw} \\ e_{gw}^k \end{Bmatrix} \quad \begin{Bmatrix} Q_{a3} \\ Q_{a3}^j \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{a3b3} & B_{a3b3}^k \\ B_{a3b3}^i & D_{a3b3}^{ik} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} g_{b3} \\ g_{b3}^k \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

N_{ab} , N_{ab}^i , \hat{N}_{ab}^j , \hat{N}_{ab}^{jp} , Q_{a3} , Q_{a3}^i , and \hat{Q}_{a3}^j are generalised stresses per unit length. A_{abgw} , B_{abgw}^i , etc, are the stiffness coefficients of the laminate which are defined as

$$(A_{abgw}, B_{abgw}^i, D_{abgw}^{ik}) = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} Q_{abgw}(1, \Psi^i, \Psi^i \Psi^k) dx_3$$

$$(A_{a_3 b_3}, B_{a_3 b_3}^i, D_{a_3 b_3}^{ik}) = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} Q_{a_3 b_3}(1, \Psi_{,3}^i, \Psi_{,3}^i \Psi_{,3}^k) dx_3 \quad (6)$$

where Q_{abgw} and $Q_{a_3 b_3}$ denote the transformed reduced stiffness coefficients. Q_{abgw} possess symmetry in the indices α and β , γ and ω , and the pairs of $\alpha\beta$ and $\gamma\omega$. The similar symmetrical property also applies to $Q_{a_3 b_3}$.

2.2. FINITE STRIP APPROXIMATION

Figure 2. A typical strip element

The whole plate is modelled with a number of finite strips along the crosswise x_2 -direction. A typical individual finite strip element is shown in figure 2. Over the strip the displacements u_a, u_3 , and u_a^i are approximated as

$$(u_\alpha, u_3, u_\alpha^i) = N^I (F \mathbf{d}_\alpha^I, F \mathbf{d}_3^I, F \mathbf{d}_\alpha^i) \quad (7)$$

Here $\mathbf{d}_a, \mathbf{d}_3$ and \mathbf{d}_a^i are column matrices of generalised displacement parameters associated with u_a, u_3 and u_a^i respectively. \mathbf{O} , row matrices, are modified B-spline function bases of order k . The superscript I denotes the number of a reference line in crosswise y -direction. N^I are the Lagrangian shape functions of order n . In the present study, the cubic B-spline function with unequal spacings is used and it is defined in a way similar to that with uniform spacings described by Dawe and Wang [13].

2.3. GOVERNOR EQUATIONS OF MOTION AND PROBLEM SOLUTION

In the absence of damping, the governor equations of the plate motion can be given through use of Hamilton's principle in terms of strain energy U , kinetic energy T and potential energy W as

$$\mathbf{M} \ddot{\mathbf{d}} + \mathbf{K} \mathbf{d} = F \mathbf{c} + \mathbf{f} \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{M} and \mathbf{K} denote the mass matrix and the effective stiffness matrix, respectively, and \mathbf{K} are functions of \mathbf{d} . \mathbf{d} and \mathbf{f} are column matrices of generalised displacement parameters and generalised force due to applied loading. F is impact contact force and \mathbf{c} is a constant column matrix.

The relationship between the contact force F and the indentation depth α is assumed as [14]

$$F = k_c \alpha^{3/2} \quad \text{when loading} \quad (9a)$$

$$F = F_m [(\alpha - \alpha_0) / (\alpha_m - \alpha_0)]^{5/2} \quad \text{when unloading} \quad (9b)$$

$$F = F_m [(\alpha - \alpha_0) / (\alpha_m - \alpha_0)]^{3/2} \quad \text{when reloading} \quad (9c)$$

where k_c is a constant. F_m denotes the maximum contact force just before unloading, α_m is the indentation corresponding to F_m , and α_0 is the permanent indentation during the loading/unloading cycle. k_c can be determined by experiment or simply calculated from the modified Hertz contact coefficient proposed by Sun⁶ as

$$k_c = \frac{4}{3} \sqrt{r_s} [(1 - \nu_s^2) / E_s + 1 / E_2]^{-1} \quad (10)$$

here r_s , ν_s and E_s are the radius, the Poisson's ratio and the Young's modulus of the impactor, respectively, and E_2 is the transverse modulus of elasticity of the plate.

Eq.9 can be expressed in a general form as

$$F = k_s (\alpha - \alpha_0)^q \quad (11)$$

here k_s and q are the contact coefficient and a constant, respectively. It is noticed that for loading, unloading and reloading process α_0 , k_s and q may be different.

The indentation depth α is the difference of the displacement of the impactor and the deflection of the reference plane of the plate at impact point, so that

$$(F / k_s)^{1/q} + \alpha_0 = v_0 t - \frac{1}{m} s - \mathbf{c}^T \mathbf{d} \quad (= \alpha) \quad (12)$$

where $s = \int_0^t \int_0^t F dt dt$

Eq.8 and Eq.12 together with appropriate initial condition define the present impact dynamic problem. It is here assumed that \mathbf{d} , $\dot{\mathbf{d}}$ and $\ddot{\mathbf{d}}$ are known at time $t=0$ and F , s , $\&$ are equal to zero at time $t=0$. In the time domain the problem can be solved with a few of different approaches. In the present investigation the solution of the problem is sought using the popular Newmark time integral algorithm. Suppose that the time period concerned is divided into a number of equal time intervals Δt and consider the satisfaction of Eq.8 and Eq.12 at time $(n+1)\Delta t$ and write

$$\mathbf{M} \ddot{\mathbf{d}}_{n+1} + \mathbf{K} \mathbf{d}_{n+1} = F_{n+1} \mathbf{c} + \mathbf{f}_{n+1} \quad (13a)$$

$$(F_{n+1} / k_s)^{1/q} + \alpha_0 = v_0 (n+1) \Delta t - \frac{1}{m} s_{n+1} - \mathbf{c}^T \mathbf{d}_{n+1} \quad (13b)$$

with approximations for \mathbf{d}_{n+1} , $\dot{\mathbf{d}}_{n+1}$, s_{n+1} and $\&_{n+1}$ as

$$\mathbf{d}_{n+1} = \mathbf{d}_n + \Delta t \dot{\mathbf{d}}_n + \frac{\Delta t^2}{2} (1 - \beta_2) \ddot{\mathbf{d}}_n + \frac{\Delta t^2}{2} \beta_2 \ddot{\mathbf{d}}_{n+1} \quad (14a)$$

$$\dot{\mathbf{d}}_{n+1} = \dot{\mathbf{d}}_n + \Delta t (1 - \beta_1) \ddot{\mathbf{d}}_n + \Delta t \beta_1 \ddot{\mathbf{d}}_{n+1}$$

$$s_{n+1} = s_n + \Delta t \&_n + \frac{\Delta t^2}{2} (1 - \beta_2) F_n + \frac{\Delta t^2}{2} \beta_2 F_{n+1} \quad (14b)$$

$$\&_{n+1} = \&_n + \Delta t (1 - \beta_1) F_n + \Delta t \beta_1 F_{n+1}$$

where parameters β_1 and β_2 can be chosen as such that good approximation properties to the algorithm are yielded. In this study the constant-average-acceleration version of Newmark method is used, and consequently, $\beta_1 = \beta_2 = 1/2$. The algorithms yield unconditional stability for linear problem at least.

Substitution of Eq.14 into Eq.13 leads to a set of non-linear equations in which the unknowns are $\ddot{\mathbf{d}}_{n+1}$ and F_{n+1} . the non-linear equations can be written in terms of residual forces as

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{M} \ddot{\mathbf{d}}_{n+1} + \mathbf{K} (\mathbf{d}_n + \Delta t \dot{\mathbf{d}}_n + \frac{\Delta t^2}{2} (1 - \beta_2) \ddot{\mathbf{d}}_n + \frac{\Delta t^2}{2} \beta_2 \ddot{\mathbf{d}}_{n+1}) - F_{n+1} \mathbf{c} - \mathbf{f}_{n+1} = 0 \quad (15a)$$

$$r = \mathbf{c}^T \mathbf{d}_{n+1} + (F_{n+1} / k_s)^{1/q} + \frac{1}{m} (s_n + \Delta t \&_n + \frac{\Delta t^2}{2} (1 - \beta_2) F_n + \frac{\Delta t^2}{2} \beta_2 F_{n+1}) + \alpha_0 - v_0 (n+1) \Delta t = 0 \quad (15b)$$

To seek the solution of the non-linear problem defined as Eq.15, the Newton-Raphson iteration scheme is here adopted. It is noted that, to the first order, Eq.15 can be approximated as

$$\mathbf{R}^{i+1} \approx \mathbf{R}^i + (\mathbf{M} + \frac{\ddot{A}t^2}{2} \beta_2 \mathbf{K}_T^i) \delta \mathbf{d}_{n+1}^i - \delta F_{n+1}^i \mathbf{c} = 0 \quad (16a)$$

$$r^{i+1} \approx r^i + \frac{\ddot{A}t^2}{2} \beta_2 \mathbf{c}^T \delta \mathbf{d}_{n+1}^i + k_i \delta F_{n+1}^i = 0 \quad (16b)$$

where

$$\mathbf{K}_T^i = \left. \frac{\partial(\mathbf{K} \mathbf{d}_{n+1})}{\partial \mathbf{d}_{n+1}} \right|_{\mathbf{d}_{n+1} = \mathbf{d}_{n+1}^i} \quad (17)$$

$$k_i = \frac{(F_{n+1}^i)^{1/q-1}}{q k_s^{1/q}} + \frac{1}{m} \frac{\ddot{A}t^2}{2} \beta_2$$

$$\delta \mathbf{d}_{n+1}^i = \mathbf{d}_{n+1}^{i+1} - \mathbf{d}_{n+1}^i \quad \delta F_{n+1}^i = F_{n+1}^{i+1} - F_{n+1}^i \quad (18)$$

here superscript i denotes the iteration counter. \mathbf{K}_T^i is the symmetric tangent stiffness matrix evaluated at iteration i . k_i is defined with the assumption of $F_{n+1}^i > 0$. $\delta \mathbf{d}_{n+1}^i$ and δF_{n+1}^i are increments, or iterative corrections, of the unknowns \mathbf{d}_{n+1} and F_{n+1} at iteration i , respectively, and they can be given from Eq.16 as

$$\delta \mathbf{d}_{n+1}^i = -(\mathbf{M} + \frac{\ddot{A}t^2}{2} \beta_2 \mathbf{K}_T^i + \frac{1}{k_i} \frac{\ddot{A}t^2}{2} \beta_2 \mathbf{c} \mathbf{c}^T)^{-1} (\mathbf{R}^i + \frac{r^i}{k_i} \mathbf{c}) \quad (19)$$

$$\delta F_{n+1}^i = -\frac{1}{k_i} (r^i + \frac{\ddot{A}t^2}{2} \beta_2 \mathbf{c}^T \delta \mathbf{d}_{n+1}^i)$$

Through use of Eq.18 with the corrections given in Eq.19, the iteration procedure results in improved solution for the unknowns \mathbf{d}_{n+1} and F_{n+1} . The procedure is repeated until the following convergence criteria are satisfied

$$\sqrt{\frac{\delta \mathbf{d}_{n+1}^i{}^T \delta \mathbf{d}_{n+1}^i}{\mathbf{d}_{n+1}^i{}^T \mathbf{d}_{n+1}^i}} < \varepsilon \quad \text{and} \quad \left| \frac{\delta F_{n+1}^i}{F_{n+1}^i} \right| < \varepsilon \quad (20)$$

where $\varepsilon = 0.0005$ is used in this work.

Up to now the impact dynamic transients are concerned with geometric non-linearity and the solution procedure is described in details as above. For comparison, the linear transient analysis of the impact problem is also investigated in this study. In fact there exists no difference between the non-linear and linear transient analyses of the impact problem in temporal approximation. Within a time step, however, the solution procedure used for the linear transient response is different from that described before for the non-linear one, and it is briefly discussed below.

In the case of linear transient analysis, the non-linear strain terms $\frac{1}{2} u_{3,\alpha} u_{3,\beta}$ is ignored in the strain-displacement relationship of Eq.3. As a result, the stiffness matrix \mathbf{K} becomes independent of the plate displacement. From Eq.15a the following equations can be given

$$(\mathbf{M} \mathbf{d}_{n+1}^e + \frac{\ddot{A}t^2}{2} \beta_2 \mathbf{K})(\mathbf{d}_{n+1}^e, \mathbf{d}_{n+1}^f) = (\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{f}_{n+1} - \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{d}_n + \ddot{A}t \mathbf{d}_n + \frac{\ddot{A}t^2}{2} (1 - \beta_2) \mathbf{d}_n)) \quad (21a)$$

$$\text{and} \quad \mathbf{d}_{n+1}^e = F_{n+1} \mathbf{d}_{n+1}^e + \mathbf{d}_{n+1}^f \quad (21b)$$

It is obvious that Eq.21a defines a set of linear algebraic equations with respect to unknowns \mathbf{d}_{n+1}^e and \mathbf{d}_{n+1}^f . Substitution of Eq.21b into Eq.15b leads to a non-linear equation with respect

to F_{n+1} , and again, the Newton-Raphson iteration technique is adopted for the solution of the non-linear equation. The iterative corrections for F_{n+1} can be written as

$$\delta F_{n+1}^i = -\frac{r^i}{k_t^i + \mathbf{c}^T \mathbf{d}_{n+1}^c} \quad (22)$$

where k_t^i and r^i are the same as those given before and \mathbf{d}_{n+1}^c are evaluated from Eq.15.

3. NUMERICAL APPLICATIONS

The above analysis procedure has been implemented in a computer software. It can be used for impact problem and, neglecting impact-related terms, for plate transient response under dynamic loading. A few of examples are presented below in details, and the selected examples of the impact problem refer to two typical kinds of low-velocity impact events, i.e. small impact mass with relatively high speed and big mass with low speed. In all the applications, the quadratic Lagrangian shape functions are applied in crosswise y -direction. The simply supported boundary conditions are defined such that the plate is simply supported for out-of-plane behaviour whilst the in-plane movement of the sides is constrained in the tangent direction but allowed in the normal direction. For the impact problems considered, the contact law is supposed as Eq.9a for both the loading and unloading processes.

3.1. ORTHOTROPIC PLATE UNDER STEP LOADING

Firstly consider the example of a square orthotropic plate under step loading studied by Chen and Dawe [15]. The plate is simply supported around all the sides and is of dimensions $A = B = 250$ mm, $h = 5$ mm. The material properties are specified as

$$E_1 = 525 \text{ Gpa}, E_2 = 21 \text{ Gpa}, \nu_{12} = 0.25,$$

$$G_{12} = G_{13} = G_{23} = 10.5 \text{ Gpa}, \rho = 800 \text{ kg/m}^3.$$

A uniformly distributed loading is suddenly applied to the plate and it keeps acting at constant magnitude during the time period concerned. Two intensity values, 1 N/mm^2 and 0.1 N/mm^2 , of uniform loading are considered. Making use of the symmetric condition, half the plate is meshed into 5 strips with 10 sections along the longitudinal direction and a numerical layer

Fig3. Central deflection of an orthotropic plate under uniform step loading

through the thickness. Fig.3 shows the results of the normalised central deflection of the plate (deflection divided by plate thickness) obtained from the present calculation with the time increment $5 \mu\text{s}$. For the higher loading level, significant difference exists between the results

of geometrically linear and non-linear solutions. It suggests that for this case ignoring geometric non-linearity may lead to unacceptable prediction of the plate response.

3.2. IMPACT OF A [0/90/0/90/0]_s PLATE

The example chosen here is the one studied by Chen and Sun [2], Liu and Dang [3]. The impact problem involves centre impact of a simply supported square T300/934 graphite/epoxy plate [0/90/0/90/0]_s with dimension 200 × 200 × 2.69 mm by a steel object with a spherical impact tip of diameter 12.7mm. The mass and the impact velocity are 19.6g and 10m/s, respectively. The material properties of the plate are defined as

$$E_1 = 120 \text{ Gpa}, E_2 = 7.9 \text{ Gpa}, \nu_{12} = 0.3$$

$$G_{12} = G_{13} = G_{23} = 5.5 \text{ Gpa},$$

$$\rho = 1580 \text{ kg/m}^3$$

For the impact problem, Chen and Sun meshed a quarter of the plate with 8×8 nine-node quadrilateral finite elements and used the contact law as given in Eq.9, whereas Liu and Dang performed their analysis using LS-DYNA3D with a 40 by 40 mesh. In the present work, the contact law defined in Eq.9a is simply employed for the whole contact process and the contact coefficient is taken as $k_c = 4.468 \times 10^4 \text{ N/mm}^{1.5}$, the same value as that used by Chen and Sun for loading process. Half the plate is divided into 10 strips with 40 sections and the time increment 1 μs is used. The contact force history and the normalised central deflection of the plate are presented in Fig.4a and Fig.4b, respectively. It is shown that the present results are well compared with those obtained from finite element method.

Fig.4. Comparison of the impact response of a [0/90/0/90/0]_s plate to a 19.6 g mass of velocity 10 m/s

3.3. QUASI-ISOTROPIC PLATE SUBJECTED TO DROP-WEIGHT IMPACT

Here we consider the example of steel drop-weight impact on a [45/0/-45/90]_s quasi-isotropic plate of AS4/3502 graphite-epoxy which was studied by Ambur et al [6]. The dimensions of the experimental specimens were 254 mm long and 127 mm wide (2 in. × 1in.) and the thickness of a single layer was 0.127 mm (0.005 in.). The specimens were simply supported on all four edges and impacted on the plate centre at impact-damage-initiation threshold energy level of 0.6779J (6 in.-lb). The material properties of AS4/3502 are given as

$$E_1 = 137.8 \text{ Gpa}, E_2 = 9.0 \text{ Gpa}, \nu_{12} = 0.3,$$

$$G_{12} = G_{13} = 6.0 \text{ Gpa}, G_{23} = 3.5 \text{ Gpa},$$

$$\rho = 1570 \text{ kg/m}^3$$

In the present investigation, the plate model is used with the dimensions 241.3 mm long by 114.3 mm wide in view of the fact that the supports are located in from the actual specimen boundaries [7]. The whole plate is modelled using 20 quadratic strips with 40 sections and through the plate thickness one numerical layer is used. The mass of the impactor is taken as 1.18 kg, whilst two different values, 25.4 mm and 12.7 mm, of impact-tip diameters are considered for comparison. The calculations are performed using a time step of 0.1 ms and the contact coefficient evaluated from Eq.10. The results of contact force are shown in Fig.5a

Fig.5. Comparison of impact response of a $[45/0/-45/90]_s$ plate to drop-weight

compared with the experimental data and the central deflection of the plate in Fig.5b. It can be found that the geometrically non-linear and linear analyses give quite different predictions for the impact response including contact force history, plate deflection and contact duration. The contact force results produced with the present geometrically non-linear analysis is closely compared with those from experiment whilst the linear analysis gives a poor prediction of the contact force. This indicates that geometric non-linearity has significant effects on the impact response and it has to be included in the analysis. It is observed that use of different impact tip diameters in the present calculation results in slightly different prediction for the contact response. In other words, the total contact force and the plate deflection are insensitive to contact coefficient. The smaller maximum contact force is corresponding to the bigger diameter of impact tip and however, this may be untrue for impact event other than the present specific case.

Fig.6. Comparison of impact response of a $[45/0/-45/90]_s$ plate to masses 1.18kg and 0.59kg at a given impact energy of 0.6779J

In an effort to understand the effect of the impact mass and velocity, analysis is also performed using an impact mass of 0.59 kg with a 12.7-mm-diameter impact tip but the

impact energy is still 0.6779J. Using different time scales the results are compared with those obtained before for impact mass 1.18 kg of 12.7-mm-diameter impact tip in Fig.6. In the figure, the time scale for 1.18 kg mass is a unit whilst the time scale for 0.59 kg mass is equal to the ratio of momenta for 1.18 kg mass and 0.59 kg, i.e., $\sqrt{2}$. It is shown that during the impact contact period the results, both contact force and plate central-deflection, corresponding to those two masses are in a close agreement when using the time scales mentioned. This indicates that for a specified drop-weight impact event, the maximum contact force and the maximum plate deflection at the impact position depend on impact energy level but the contact period is dominated by the impact mass and longer contact period arises from bigger impact mass.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A B-spline finite strip model has been developed in the context of a layer-wise plate theory for analysing the geometrically non-linear response of laminated composite plates to transverse low-velocity impact. To simplify the complicated contact analysis, a Hertz-type contact law is incorporated into the finite strip model for accounting for the contact behaviour. The solution of the non-linear impact problem is sought using Newmark time integration scheme in conjunction with Newton-Raphson iteration. The geometrically linear transient analysis of the impact problem is briefly discussed as well. With neglecting impact-related terms, the developed procedure is capable of analysing plate transients under dynamic loading.

The capability of the model has been used in a few of applications including the transient analysis of the plate under given dynamic loading and the impact response analysis of the plate subjected to relatively-high- and low-velocity impactors. Comparison of the results obtained from the geometrically non-linear analysis is made with those of small-deflection solution and/or available results gained from finite element calculation and experiment. This comparison demonstrates the validity of the analysis procedure as well as the effect of geometric non-linearity on plate response and contact force. The results show that for a specified drop-weight impact event, the impact energy level dominates the maximum contact force and the maximum plate deflection at the impact position but the impact mass dominates the impact contact duration.

The analysis capability of the present model is being extended for predicting the initiation and propagation of the low-velocity impact damage through introduction of appropriate failure criteria and failure models. The related work will be reported separately.

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